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Perception and Implementation of Digitalization in Teacher Education Curriculum in Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State

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Abstract

This study investigated a comparative analysis between perception and implementation of Digitalization in Teacher Education Curriculum in Federal College Education, Owerri, Imo State. The comparative research design was adopted for the study. Five schools were randomly selected from the Federal Colleges of Education, in Owerri, Imo State. Fifty pre-service teachers were randomly selected for each school, making a total of 250 pre-service teachers, while five lecturers were randomly selected from each school, making a total of 25 lecturers. In all, a total of 250 students and 25 lecturers participated in the study. Two research instruments were used for data collection: Perception of Digitalization of Teacher Education Curriculum Questionnaire ($r=0.74$) and Pre-service Teachers' Digitalisation of Teacher Education Curriculum Questionnaire ($r=0.75$). Data collected were analysed using percentage, frequency count, mean and standard deviation. Results revealed that lecturers' perception of the level of digitalization in implementation of teacher education curriculum in colleges of education was negative because the weighted mean of 2.38 was below the threshold set at 2.50. The weighted mean of 2.27 which is lower than the threshold set at 2.50. This implies that pre-service teachers had a negative perception of the level of Digitalization in the implementation of teacher education curriculum. The result revealed that there was a positive strong relationship between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of Digitalization in the implementation of teacher education curriculum ($r = .626$; $p = .001 < .05$). While, lecturers and pre-service teachers should have positive perceptions towards the Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that curriculum planners should Digitalised the teacher education curriculum.

Keyword: (*Keywords: Education, Curriculum, Digitalisation, Lecturers', Pre-service Teacher*)

Introduction

Teacher Education can be described as the policies, procedures and provisions that are mainly designed to equip pre-service teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, behaviours and skills that are required to make the performance of their task effective in the classroom, school and the society at large. This is essential if quality education is to be achieved in any nation, this is unconnected with the fact that the quality of teachers at the basic level of education in Nigeria has been a major concern to stakeholders, especially the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) which has the responsibility for granting accreditation for all academic programmes in Colleges of Education in Nigeria, monitoring of curriculum implementation and providing other quality assurance services in the production of quality teachers to facilitate quality education through effective teaching and learning process in the country (Olatunji, 2021).

Suraasa (2024), define teacher education as the educational programme that is specifically designed to equip potential teachers and those already on the job with the required cognitive knowledge (relevant to their areas of specialization); affective dispositions (good interpersonal relationship and personal disposition) and psychomotor competencies (resourcefulness and adaptability skills) relevant to the task they are expected to perform. While, Izuagba and Obiefuna (2019) sees teacher education as the policies and procedures designed to equip prospectivae teachers with the knowledge, attitude, behaviours and skills they require to perform their task effectively in the classroom. According to the national policy on education (FRN, 2004; 2013), teacher education programme shall be structured to equip teachers for effective performance of their duties. It is on this basis that Ekundayo and Lawal (2016) describe education in general and teacher education in particular, as been fundamental to the construction of ideas required in a knowledge driven economy. To them, the development of pre-service teachers' cognitive perspective is crucial to their effectiveness as it ensures that they acquire mastery of the subject matter they are expected to

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teach. Similarly, the development of affective disposition makes it possible for them to acquire inter-personal and intra-personal skills necessary for creating conducive atmosphere for learning. It will also make them strive to understand the learners, their difficulties and capabilities in order to adequately help them learn and relate with other learners.

Teacher education is the preparation given to an individual to help them deal with procedures provision and policies, best teaching skills, attitudes and behaviours that would help them to help learners acquire knowledge about various concepts effectively in any environment (classroom or school). Therefore, teacher education is an important factor because it is the process of initiating, preparing pre-service teachers, retraining of existing teachers in schools, and equipping them with relevant experiences, skills and competencies to tackle the responsibilities of education profession effectively. If teacher education is attended to properly, it will develop capacity building and keep pre-service teachers abreast of latest teaching skills that will prepare them to interact well with students in the classroom (Okeke, 2012). Teacher education is thereby noted as crucial for pre-service teachers are prepared through the programme to teach the born and unborn generations of teachers who will control the affairs of the nation. Since it has been generally recognised that teacher education is key to improve students learning opportunities. Therefore, teacher education should be managed in such a way that the rapid changing socio-economic and political environment should be attended to in such a way teacher education would no longer be seen as a programme that would prepare pre-service teachers for teaching job only, but rather a programme that would inculcate in learner other skills, such as learning-to-learn skills, as well as the inculcation of knowing yourself, or developing the best in you (intra-personal skills) with knowing and getting along with other skills (intra-personal skills). The purpose of investing in teacher preparation programme should be with the ultimate goal of producing effective teachers that will perform optimally on the job. Teacher education that will produce professional and well-qualified teachers that can meet up with the changing needs of the learners and the society as a whole. Aglazor (2017), describe a teacher as someone who has been professionally trained in such institutions designed for the purpose to help learners move from a state of ignorant to a state of knowledge. While, to Mkpa (2012), he asserted that the teacher is incontrovertibly the fulcrum on which the system of education stands.

The National Policy on Education recognises the importance of teacher development and states that no system of education can rise above the quality of its teachers (FGN, 2013). If the teacher has such influence on the quality of students' achievement in the subject, then a critical look at what the teacher education is, where it is supposed to be and where it should be prepared for cannot be ignored without facing grievous consequences. The primary focus of teacher training institutions is teacher production towards quality education at all levels. The specific objectives of teacher education are to: (a) produce highly motivated conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of educational system (b) encourage further the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers (c) help teachers to fit into social life of the community and the society at large and enhance their commitment to national goals (d) provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and make them adaptable to changing situations (e) enhance teachers' commitment to the teaching profession (FRN, 2013). Andrew and Henry (2024) explain that curriculum implementation is the process of putting all that has been planned as a curriculum document into practice in the classroom through the combined efforts of teachers, learners, school administrators, and parent, as well as interaction with facilities, instructional materials, instructional strategies and psychological and social environment. Obanya (2020) also defined curriculum implementation as day-to day activities which the school management and classroom teachers undertake in the pursuit of the objective of any given curriculum. Braimoh (2017), describe curriculum implementation as a deliberate plan through which learners will be made to interact with the content knowledge, learning activities and learning materials to acquire expected learning outcomes. However, to Mkpa and Izuagba (2012), curriculum implementation takes place in the classroom, they describe it as the execution of the planned curriculum, using curriculum materials that have been developed for that purpose. They explained further that, it is at this stage that the learners for whom the programme is planned, interact with the content and materials in order to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes and abilities. It was posited that the arduous task of implementing the curriculum lies on the teacher. In addition, Mkpa (1987) asserted that the task of translating the curriculum document into operating curriculum by the joint efforts of learners, teachers and other interest groups. In other words, curriculum implementation is that stage in the curriculum process where the learner through the mediation of the teacher, interacts with learning activities so that learning is maximized, as reflected in the new behaviour acquired by the learner. The arduous task of implementing the curriculum lies on the teacher. It is arduous because the teacher does not implement the content of the curriculum plan as it is, doing this will not be realistic, rather he breaks down the content into teachable units. As a matter of fact, what comes to the teacher is not the curriculum plan, rather what the teacher gets is the syllabus, which is derived from the curriculum plan. The teacher breaks down the content of the syllabus to derive the scheme of work. Finally, the lesson plan is worked out from the unit plan.

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A teacher that is misinformed or that lacks appropriate skills can affect the implementation of the curriculum. It must therefore be noted that curriculum implementation is that time that the teacher brought the learners into contact with the curriculum that has been planned for them, using curriculum materials that have been developed for that purpose, which most of the time takes place in the classroom (Popoola, 2024).

According to Strayer (2012), education is not limited to the physical classroom anymore because technology is now being used to offer education to learners residing anywhere in the globe. For teacher education curriculum to be well implemented in this era, it needs to be digitalised. Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014) described digitalisation as a process of integrating digital technologies into all aspects of business and society, fundamentally altering the way organisations operate and deliver value. Schwab (2016) characterised digitalisation as a key aspect of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, marked by the convergence of digital, physical, and biological systems. He emphasizes how technologies like AI, IoT, and robotics are transforming industries and societal structures. According to Westerman, Bonnet and McAfee (2014), digitalisation is the use of digital technologies to transform business processes, customer interactions, and organisational culture. This involves not just technology adoption but also fundamental changes in how businesses operate.

Porter and Heppelmann (2014) asserted that digitalisation involves the integration of smart, connected products that drive new forms of competition and innovation. They focus on how these technologies are reshaping business strategies and industry dynamics. Zuboff (2019) defined digitalisation through the lens of surveillance capitalism, Zuboff argued that the pervasive collection and analysis of digital data for commercial purposes have significant implications for privacy, power, and social control. Frey and Osborne (2013) analysed digitalisation in terms of its impact on employment, specifically how advances in automation and digital technologies are likely to affect job markets and skill requirements. Cohen (2012) examined digitalisation in the context of legal and ethical issues, focusing on how the integration of digital technologies affects privacy, data protection, and regulatory frameworks. Bates (2015) defined digitalisation in education as the use of digital technologies to enhance teaching and learning. Bate highlighted how digital tools can transform educational practices and learning outcomes. Gardner (2014) explored how digitalisation influences educational practices, emphasising the need for educational systems to adapt to new technologies and pedagogical approaches to better prepare learners for the digital age.

Statement of the Statement of the Problem

Teacher education is a formal and systematic process of preparing pre-service teachers for the task ahead. Despite the importance attached to teacher education curriculum, it was discovered that its curriculum is not well implemented. As a way of addressing this problem scholars have carried out numerous studies, such as Lawal (2019), Waseka, Simatina and Okwach (2016) and Ogbulogo (2011). Although, most of these studies came up with good insights to teacher education curriculum but with less emphasis on digitalisation of teacher education curriculum, especially in colleges of education. Therefore, this study was set to do a Comparative Analysis Between Perception and Implementation in Teacher Education Curriculum in Federal Colleges of Education, Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?
2. What are pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?
3. What relationship exists between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?

Methodology

The survey research design was adopted for the study. Five schools were randomly selected from schools in Colleges of Education in Owerri, Imo State. Fifty pre-service teachers were randomly selected for each school, making a total of 250 pre-service teachers. Five lecturers were randomly selected from each school, making a total of 25 lecturers. In all, a total of 250 students and 25 lecturers participated in the study. Two research instruments were used for data collection: Perception of Digitalisation of Teacher Education Curriculum Questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha was used to establish the reliability coefficient and it gave an index of ($r=0.74$) and Pre-service Teachers' Digitalisation of Teacher Education Curriculum Questionnaire. Cronbach alpha was used to established the reliability coefficient and it gave an index of ($r=0.75$). Data collected were analysed using percentage, frequency count, mean and standard deviation

Results

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Research Question One:

What are lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?

Table 1: Lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum in

S/N	Items	Mean	Std. D.
1	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum promotes teaching.	1.84	.85
2	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes lecturers to be hardworking.	2.16	1.06
3	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes lecturers to have good attitude towards teaching.	2.40	1.00
4	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum stimulates lecturers' ability to think very fast.	2.24	.830
5	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum is not objective.	2.08	1.15
6	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum changes teachers' attitude towards teaching.	2.40	1.08
7	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students learn new things.	2.31	.945
8	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum is a challenging activity.	2.76	.969
9	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum facilitates the development of students' competence.	2.72	1.10
10	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum does not develop students' learning ability.	2.52	.770
11	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to be passive recipient of knowledge.	2.20	1.00
12	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to have positive attitude towards learning.	2.32	.802
13	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum changes teachers' wrong impression about teaching.	2.16	1.17
14	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students reflect on what they learnt.	2.12	1.09
15	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum increases students' interest in learning.	2.24	1.12
16	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students attend Arabic language classroom regularly.	2.41	1.10
17	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to enjoy.	2.52	1.00
18	Digitalisation of contents of teacher education curriculum is not easy to teach.	2.56	1.00
19	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum fosters teaching of the curriculum.	2.64	.952
20	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to be eager to learn.	2.92	.862
Weighted mean = 2.38; Threshold = 2.50			

Table 1 shows the lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. However, the lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum was negative because the weighted mean of 2.38 was below the threshold set at 2.50.

Research Question Two:

What are pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?

Table 2: Pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum

S/N	Items	Mean	St. D.
1	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum promotes teaching.	1.94	.886

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2	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes lecturers to be hardworking.	1.89	.989
3	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes lecturers to have good attitude towards teaching.	2.02	1.02
4	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum stimulates lecturers' ability to think very fast.	2.13	1.08
5	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum is not objective.	1.91	1.04
6	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum changes teachers' attitude towards teaching.	2.13	.979
7	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students learn new things.	2.03	.838
8	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum is a challenging activity.	1.97	.939
9	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum facilitates the development of students' competence.	2.16	1.06
10	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum does not develop students' learning ability.	2.62	.885
11	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to be passive recipient of knowledge.	2.77	1.10
12	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to have positive attitude towards learning.	2.19	.930
13	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum changes teachers' wrong impression about teaching.	1.92	1.05
14	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students reflect on what they learnt.	2.08	.991
15	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum increases students' interest in learning.	2.24	.865
16	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students attend Arabic language classroom regularly.	2.51	1.25
17	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to enjoy.	2.55	1.17
18	Digitalisation of contents of teacher education curriculum is not easy to teach.	2.74	.868
19	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum fosters teaching of the curriculum.	2.69	.939
20	Digitalisation of teacher education curriculum makes students to be eager to learn.	2.96	1.06
Weighted Mean = 2.27; Threshold = 2.50			

Table 2 shows the pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. The weighted mean of 2.27 which is lower than the threshold set at 2.50. It implies that pre-service teachers had a negative perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum.

Research Question Three:

What relationship exists between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum?

Table 3: Relationship that exists between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum

Variables	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	r	p-value	Sig.
Lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum	25	47.16	11.01	.626	.001	Sig.
Pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum	25	45.41	8.09			

Table 3 shows the relationship exists between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum using the Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. The result revealed that

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there was a positive strong relationship between lecturers' and pre-service teachers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum ($r = .626$; $p = .001 < .05$). This implies that a direct relationship existed between how lecturers and pre-service teachers perceived the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum

Discussion of Findings

Table I revealed that lecturers' perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. The finding of this study is in line with Lawal (2019) who found that teachers' perception of the level of implementation of English Studies was negative. The finding is contrary to Adegoke (2018) who found that teachers had positive perception of the curriculum objectives of English Studies curriculum.

Table II revealed that pre-service teachers had a negative perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. This is in line with the study of Waseka, Simatwa and Okwach (2016) revealed that students had a negative perception of curriculum implementation. This is against the finding of Ogbulogo (2011) who revealed that students had a negative perception of curriculum implementation.

Table III revealed that a direct relationship existed between how lecturers and pre-service teachers perceived the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. This finding is in line with Lawal (2019) who found that there was relationship between teachers and students' perception of English Studies curriculum. This is contrary to the study of Adegoke (2018) who reported that there was relationship between teachers and students' perception of English Studies curriculum.

Conclusion

The study has shown that lecturers and pre-service teachers had a negative perception of the level of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum. Based on the findings, this study has provided a better understanding of the place of digitalisation in implementation of teacher education curriculum.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. Curriculum planners and developers should digitalise the teacher education curriculum.
2. Lecturers and pre-service teachers should develop a positive perception to the digitalisation of teacher education curriculum.
3. Government should do everything possible to educate lecturers' and pre-service teachers on why teacher education curriculum needs to be digitalised.

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